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Sandalinayan Sirig sa Minilalansay Lena

Bantogen walking forward on the vast seashore, day and night looking for a place called Minilalansay Lena where he heard from the nori bird named Diwata ko Rendingan about the tale of a beautiful princess Sandalinayan Sirig. She was hidden in the island of Molopolo Legawan, tightly well-guarded, surrounded by howling winds, and encircled by a blazing blast of fire. No one is allowed to enter this island except her family in Minilalansay Lena. The Ayonan Mindamedag sworn that any datu who will enter this fortified isle, well-guarded by a blazing fire will be the husband of the fair princess.

The prince went through directly to this island. He caught a splendid sight of three walls surrounding the place and doors made of strong steel as he now climbed the stairs up to the waiting area of the lamin trying to spot the princess who lived away from her real home. A maidservant had spotted the royal presence of the prince, informing the royal princess about the arrival of this handsome prince.

The princess was now having doubts and feeling disturbed, hence her wise servant Kilaman invited the visitor to come in and betel quid was served, however the princess warned the prince to go back to where he come from for visiting the island is prohibited so that people would not know where she lives as sworn by his king. The princess suggested him to proceed down to Lalansayan a Lena to take his rest, willing to give him gifts and rare heirlooms to persuade him to leave, only considering him as brother, so as not to break the rules commanded by traditions. The princess futher added that if he would not take his leave, she will go down instead down to Lalansayan a Lena.

Immediately the prince asked permission to leave so now the princess commanded the palace maidservants to guard the lamin as she would be asleep for the mean time. In contrary, the prince did not go but instead, asked help from the Diwata ko Bembaran to adduct the princess all the way to Malinday Bembaran. Princess Lawanen, together with her look-alike Ikada, saw the enchantment of an object passing by in the air where Prince Bantogen alarmed her dear sister not to be frightened for the princess of Lalansayan a Lena whom he believed to be an asset and add to the fame of Bembaran so take care of her as he took his leave.

Meanwhile, the princess Salindayan Sirig has awoken from a deep sleep and her tears falling down. Ikada comforted her when Aya Paganay Ba'i, Walain sa Masamar, and Walain sa Poregen approached the splendid bed acknowledging her as high-ranking princess from pure ancestry. Ayonan Pangadapen formally addressed her about their plans to ask her hand for marriage where the ten boats were filled with rare treasures to be offered as dowry in Milalansay a Lena through Bantogen. Soon, the princess hesitantly agreed under certain conditions.